

Local identity, culture, & city branding: Triangle paradigm of tourism development of Purwakarta

Saepudin

Islamic University "45" Bekasi, Bekasi, Indonesia, af.unisma@gmail.com

Abstract

Nowdays, tendency of global tourism is changed over from high volume production of standard commodities into high value production of unique commodities. This paradigm emphasize on authenticity, originality, and uniqueness. The change of tourism tendency implicate on principal, type, place branding, and the way of promoting the tourism potential on each district in Indonesia. Purwakarta Regency Government promotes program "*balik ka lembur*" (back to nature) as the way of branding and promotes localness (Sundanese Culture). By this program, Purwakarta develops tourism tractive powers, and it as the way of preservation on nature, culture and identity of people in Purwakarta. Development and enforcement of this program produce localness tourism i.e. specific, unique, and authenticity of Purwakarta. Purwakarta implemented this concept on local dress (Sundanese), local culture symbol, local infrastructure, local habit, local art, traditional craft, local life style, government policy on daily language, etc. Purwakarta emerged history moreover Sundanese mythology, nature, art, and culture of Sundanese. These are not only the way Purwakarta promotes its potential of tourism but also these are the way of branding (city branding).

Keywords: city branding; marketing tourism communication; localness;

1. Introduction

There is an increasingly visible trend of global tourism today. Tourists tend to abandon high volume production of standard commodities and move on to high value production of unique commodities that highlight on authenticity, originality and local uniqueness. The trends of tourism increasingly spread and the number of travelers allocentric typology, ie tourists only want to visit places that have not been known, adventurous, and want to take advantage of facilities provided by local communities become a great opportunity in developing nature-based tourism and culture-based tourism (Sugihamretha. et.al, 2015).

By increasing this market trends then appear different model of development and representation of tourism in some areas, especially if the target market is foreign tourists. This makes culture as tourism commodity, even Urry calls it 'the cultural industry' (in Robinson & Phipps, 2005). By this means, as a cultural industry, tourism will create a cultural transformation of an area, the geographical space must be transformed into a tourist destination or a tourist site and should be based on local cultural contexts in accordance with the tastes of global tourism market trends (Papen in Robinson & Phipps, 2005).

It must be represented in various aspects, cultural expressions should be displayed, language behavior, actions, activities of the community must be able to explain the region and its people (Linknud in Robinson & Phipps, 2005), even the formation of regional myths can be presented or even created (Lash & Urry in Robinson & Phipps, 2005). Tourism managers, in this case may also the government, especially local governments must create a view of the region with some images that have been selected, symbols, and devices that have associative value with the culture of society in the region.

By promoting the perspective of tourism discourse, Purwakarta District Government seeks to transform the represented culture in the form of geographical space, cultural expression, language behavior, actions, community activities, even the formation of local myth based on local culture deliberately presented, images, symbols and instruments associate with value of the culture of society in this area was also presented.

Purwakarta District Government represented the value of local culture as part of place branding. The term development of tourism "balik ka lembur (back to nature)" which is associate with the image and theme of the Sundanese presented into the theme of tourism development Purwakarta. By this theme, Purwakarta District developed tourist appeal based on nature and Sundanese culture. This development of tourism is also an effort to preserve the natural and cultural as well as the development of the identity of the Purwakarta people. The effort is applied by developing tourist appeals through the common theme of Sundanese culture, in the form of a series of nodes of historical aspects, nature, art and culture of West Java. Through the development and enforcement of the theme, which then rooted in the nature and culture of Sunda, finally constructed the specific tourism, unique and typical tourism of Purwakarta.

2. Method

This research is qualitative. The selection of this approach is based on the problems and objectives of the research, as well as the object of research related to the discourse analysis of the development of tourism marketing communication of Purwakarta Regency, covering many aspects ranging from policy to marketing application including in the design of identity, culture and city image.

The main object that will explore more deeply by this research are facts of development of tourism in Purwakarta regency along with its tourism marketing attributes, including the construction of the identity, culture and image of the city. The researcher attempts to understand the pattern of tourism marketing communication conducted by the Purwakarta regency government, and describes it by explaining the causes of the action and giving meaning of it.

This research focus on three main aspects of tourism marketing communications conducted by Purwakarta government i.e construction of city identity, regional culture and city image. Therefore analysis start from the related policy to the implementation of it. In my opinion, the efforts of Purwakarta Regency government in terms of construction of city identity, regional culture and urban image is constructed systemically, scheduled and applied in government and social order. Then I uses discourse analysis especially tourism discourse which starts from ideology analysis as base of tourism development, constructed discourses, pattern and form of ideology construction which become tourism discourse typical of Purwakarta. The ideology that deliberately expressed by the regional leaders, its application and its relevance to identity, culture and image of the city.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 *Ideology and Tourism Discourse of Purwakata*

In perspective of critical discourse, tourism representation is well-known as tourism imagination that seeks to present narrative fantasies and 'dream spaces' of some tourism potential such as the depiction of cultural diversity (Laing & Crouch 2009; Wood, 1998; Montero, 2011 in Jiang, 2013). Tourism managers play the role of a social agent of construction of reality in creating a picture of tourism as the expectation of tourists (Adam in Jiang, 2013). There are various methods of application of tourism discourse such as the use of various signs intended to bring the effects of tourism communication (van Leeuwen, 2004 in Ip, 2008). Various modes of communication (multimodality) are used to present a picture of tourism such as language, images, graphics, typography all combined in an integrative way to assist travelers in determining where to visit (van Leeuwen in Ip, 2008).

Urry (in Jaworski & Pritchard, 2005) stresses on the importance of presenting space and space construction. According to him, the place is constructed intersubjectively and shows forces of the psychological, ideological and meaning of feeling. The construction of the place is able to develop a long-standing interest on the tourist experience. Ideology in the discourse has been the concern of many scholars such as Fowler, 1985; Billig, 1990, 1991; Van Dijk, 1998 (in Jaworski & Pritchard, 2005) ideology is a set of social representations (common and abstract) shared by members of social groups and used by them to complete daily social practices such as acting and interacting (communicating). These representations are administered in systems propagated by social classes and other groups in order to make meaningful in the way of social practises (Hall in Jaworski & Pritchard, 2005).

On perspective of tourism discourse, Purwakarta Regency Government seeks to transform the represented culture in the form of geographical space, cultural expression, language behavior, actions, community activities, even the construction of local myth based on local culture deliberately presented, images, symbols and instruments associate with the culture of local community (Sunda). Purwakarta Regency Government presents value of local culture as part of place branding.

Purwakarta Regency Government promotes program “*balik ka lembur*” (back to nature) as the way of branding and promotes localness (Sundanese Culture). By this program, Purwakarta develops tourism tractive powers, and it as the way of preservation on nature, culture and identity of people in Purwakarta. Development and enforcement of this program produce localness tourism i.e. specific, unique, and authenticity of Purwakarta. Purwakarta implemented this concept on local dress (Sundanese), local culture symbol, local infrastructure, local habit, local art, traditional craft, local life style, government policy on daily language, etc. Purwakarta emerged history moreover Sundanese mythology, nature, art, and culture of Sundanese (Nuryanto, Ahdiyati, Maknun, 2016).

3.2 *Locality and City Branding of Purwakarta*

Strategy of recognition and application of local culture (Sundanese) became a cultural treasure that must be considered, not only by the Purwakarta community but general in West Java. This is indicated by spreading identity of local culture in Purwakarta area in particular and in West Java generally. Then it became a specific local power Purwakarta in rebranding it as city of culture-based tourism (Sunda). The three concepts (local identity, culture, and city branding) which have been formulated by Dedi Mulyadi (Kang Dedi / Purwakarta Regent) became a symbol of pride for some people in the area, although actually he changed the branding of Purwakarta as religious city into cultural city of Sunda.

The image itself is very closely related to the identity of tourism area. Many people consider the importance of these, so they attempt to construct images and identities that are then delivered in a massive and integrative way to potential tourists. Especially in today's era every tourism destination not only competes with local tourism destination but also international scale (Kotler in Riza, Doratli, Fasli, 2012).

Branding is a product of development and marketing activity that elevates the value of a product with unique characteristics deliberately designed to define a product for the intended consumer as well as the basis for the company or institution in developing other products (Donald, Kofman, Kevin, 2009). Kapferer (in Ochkovskaya, 2016) provides a concise definition of the brand as a set of associate values, a name with the power of persuading the market. Some scholars such as Skinner affirmed the importance of city brand. He (in Ahmad, Abdullah, Tamam, Bolong, 2013) stated that brands must communicate a consistent identity and distinction between established identity and the identity understood by the people of a city are able in creating a strong and positive image of a city. The identity itself must derive from the distinctive characteristics of a city, its value and benefits (Ochkovskaya, 2016).

Another thing that should also be formulated in the creation of a city brand is the need to 'design the culture', which means to bring the element of culture to cover the image of the city that has already exist in the minds of tourists.

Reference

- Donald, Stephanie Hemelryk., Kofman, Eleonore, & Kevin, Catherine. 2009. *Branding Cities: Cosmopolitanism, Parochialism, and Social Change*. Routledge: New York.
- Ip, Janice Yui Ling. 2008. *Analyzing Tourism Discourse: A Case Study of Hong Kong Travel Brochure*. LCOM Papers 1: 1-19.
- Jaworski, Adam & Pritchard, Annette (ed). 2005. *Discourse, Communication and Tourism*. Channel View Publications: Clevedon.
- Jiang, Keyin. 2013. *Tourism Discourse and Its Knowledge in Najiahu Village*. Cambridge Journal of China Studies Volume 10, No. 1.
- Ochkovskaya, Marina. 2016. *Bucharest as A City Brand: How to Attract Russian Tourists*. Management & Marketing. Volume XIV. Issue 1/2016.
- Nuryanto, Ahdiyat, Maknun. 2016. Perencanaan dan Perancangan Desa Wisata Kampung Tajur Kahuripan di Kab. Purwakarta-Jawa Barat Berbasiskan Arsitektur Tradisional Sunda
- Sugihamretha, Dewa Gde. Et.all. 2015. Strategi kebijakan perencanaan pembangunan pariwisata di pulau-pulau kecil sebagai pusat pertumbuhan. <http://www.bappenas.go.id/index.php?Cid=8595>.
- Robinson, Mike & Phipps, Alison. 2005. *Tourism and Cultural Change*. Channel View Publications. Toronto.
- Riza, Müge., Doratli, Naciye & Fasli, Mukaddes. 2012. *City Branding and Identity*. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 35: 293 – 300.